

ENVIRONMENTALLY-INFORMED, DATA-DRIVEN PRECAST CONCRETE BRIDGE CONDITION MODELING FOR FUTURE-PROOF TRANSPORTATION INFRASTRUCTURE

Praneeth Shivashankarappa¹, Eun Jeong Cha¹

¹University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, Urbana, IL, USA

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Eun Jeong Cha, ejcha@illinois.edu

Abstract:

Bridge deterioration is governed by complex interactions between structural characteristics, traffic loading, and environmental exposure. Existing deterioration models often rely on historical inspection data and coarse environmental descriptors, limiting their ability to capture variability induced by environmental conditions. This study develops an environmentally informed, data-driven framework for modeling bridge condition, focusing on precast concrete bridges. A dataset combining National Bridge Inventory data, traffic metrics, and detailed NOAA environmental variables was constructed for over 2,400 precast Illinois bridges. Multinomial logistic regression and neural network models were applied, with AIC-based feature selection improving generalization. Results show that environmental factors, particularly precipitation and snowfall, significantly influence condition classification, with indicating notable shifts in condition distributions by changing environmental conditions. An XGBoost-based counterfactual analysis with SHAP interpretability reveals that deck type effects are age-dependent, with precast bridges showing mid-life advantages. The framework enables scalable integration of environmental effects for improved infrastructure planning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental stressors such as temperature variability, humidity, precipitation, and freeze–thaw cycles significantly influence material degradation and long-term structural performance and have been identified as key drivers of bridge deterioration (Liu and El-Gohary, 2022; Liu and Zhang, 2020; Liu et al., 2018; Huang et al., 2010). Traditional deterioration models, including Markov-based and regression-based approaches, rely primarily on historical inspection data and structural attributes (Morcoux, 2006; Mishalani and Madanat, 2002; Estes and Frangopol, 2001), but do not adequately capture site-specific environmental variability and its temporal evolution, particularly for precast concrete bridges. This study addresses this gap by developing an integrated framework that jointly considers structural, traffic, and environmental variables to model bridge conditions under varying environmental conditions.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. First, the methodology for data integration and model development is presented, including the construction of a multi-source dataset and the implementation of both statistical and machine learning models. Next, model performance is evaluated, with emphasis on the role of environmental variables and feature selection in improving predictive capability. The framework is then applied to assess bridge conditions under extended environmental scenarios to examine sensitivity to changing conditions. Finally, a comparative analysis between precast

and cast-in-place (CIP) bridges is conducted using interpretable machine learning techniques to provide insights into differences in performance across bridge types.

2. DATA-DRIVEN BRIDGE CONDITION MODEL DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Data Integration

This study focuses on precast concrete bridges located in Illinois, USA, using data corresponding to the year 2022. A multi-source dataset was developed by integrating structural, traffic, and environmental variables, resulting in over 2,300 bridges with 37 explanatory variables. Bridge and traffic data were obtained from the FHWA National Bridge Inventory (NBI) (FHWA, 2022), including condition ratings, geometric properties, and traffic metrics such as AADT and truck percentage. Environmental data were sourced from the NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI) (NOAA, 2022), with future projections obtained from CMIP6 datasets (WCRP, 2025). Environmental observations were originally available at daily and monthly resolutions and were aggregated into annual metrics to align with bridge inspection intervals. Temperature variables were summarized using annual mean, maximum, and minimum values; precipitation and snowfall were computed as annual totals; and relative humidity was averaged annually. Additionally, heating and cooling degree days (HDD/CDD) were derived from daily temperature records.

Each bridge was assigned environmental exposure by mapping it to the nearest of four representative weather stations across Illinois, namely: Chicago (USW00094846), Moline (USW00014923), Peoria (USW00014842), and Quincy (USW00093821) airports. This approach provides consistent regional coverage while maintaining consistency in environmental characterization. The integrated dataset structure and variables are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Integrated data sources and parameters used for bridge condition modeling.

Data Type	Parameters	Source
Bridge Data	Condition Ratings (Items 58, 59, 60, 62, 67), Material, Location	FHWA NBI
Traffic Data	AADT (029), % Truck Traffic (109), Functional Class (026)	FHWA NBI
Structural Features	Span length, structure length, skew angle, vertical clearance, design load	FHWA NBI
Environmental Data	Annual Mean/Max/Min Temperature, Precipitation, Snowfall, Humidity	NOAA NCEI
	HDD, CDD, Diurnal Temperature Range	Derived from NOAA NCEI
	Projected Environmental Values	WCRP CMIP6

2.2. Model Development and Structure

Two target variables derived from the NBI inspection data were considered for the modeling. The first is the structural evaluation rating, a nine-level scale from 9 (excellent) to 0 (failed) representing overall structural adequacy. The second is a three-class bridge condition variable defined using the lowest rating among deck, superstructure, substructure, and culvert components, classified as Good (≥ 7), Fair (5 - 6), and Poor (≤ 4), ensuring that the condition reflects the most critical deficiency.

Two supervised learning approaches were employed to model bridge deterioration: multinomial logistic regression (MLR) and a feedforward neural network (multi-layer perceptron, MLP). Using MLR, the probability of a bridge belonging to class k is estimated by Eq. (1).

$$P(Y_i = k | X_i) = \frac{\exp(\beta_k^T X_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^C \exp(\beta_j^T X_i)} \quad (1)$$

where Y_i is the target class label for bridge i , X_i is the input feature vector, k is the class index, β_k is the coefficient vector corresponding to class k , C is the total number of classes. MLR provides interpretable relationships between predictors and class membership. Using MLP, nonlinear interactions can be captured (Kong et al., 2023; Hastie et al., 2009). The neural network model architecture was selected through validation-based tuning to balance predictive performance and overfitting. The selected MLP consisted of three hidden layers (64 - 32 - 16 neurons) with ReLU activation and a softmax output layer.

To improve model performance, feature selection and class imbalance correction were applied. AIC-based backward elimination reduced the initial set of 37 variables to 10 key predictors, including structural attributes (year built, design load, skew angle, structure length), clearance characteristics (vertical clearance), performance indicators (operating and inventory ratings), condition indicators (scour critical status), and environmental variables (precipitation and snowfall), thereby reducing model complexity and overfitting. Additionally, class weighting was implemented to address imbalance in the dataset, where the majority of bridges were classified as “Good,” by penalizing misclassification of minority classes while preserving the original data distribution.

2.3. Model Performance and Results

Following feature selection and class imbalance correction, both MLR and MLP models demonstrate similar predictive performance. The MLR achieved ~72% accuracy, while the MLP achieved ~74% for bridge condition prediction. For the nine-class structural evaluation, both models showed lower performance, with accuracies of ~36% and ~37%, respectively, reflecting the increased difficulty of predicting finer condition states. The comparable performance of the two models suggests that linear relationships capture a substantial portion of the underlying deterioration patterns, while the MLP provides marginal improvements (<2%) in capturing nonlinear effects.

The reduction in dimensionality enhanced model interpretability while improving predictive accuracy by ~10% for the nine-level scale and by ~20% for the three-class bridge condition classification. Class weighting improved average class-wise accuracy by approximately ~7% for bridge condition prediction, while its impact on structural evaluation was negligible. For both models and both target variables, misclassifications were primarily observed between adjacent condition classes, consistent with the ordinal nature of bridge condition ratings.

3. DATA-DRIVEN BRIDGE CONDITION MODEL APPLICATION

3.1. Bridge Condition Prediction

To evaluate the environmental sensitivity of bridge condition, the trained models were applied using projected environmental inputs for 2050 and 2100, while other variables were held constant to isolate environmental effects. Under the 2050 scenario, both models predict a decrease in Good bridges (MLR -12.68%, MLP -15.63%) and an increase in Poor bridges (MLR +101.68%, MLP +93.85%), indicating accelerated deterioration. By 2100, the Good category is eliminated (MLR -100%, MLP -100%), with substantial increases in Fair (MLR +125.67%, MLP +232.20%) and Poor (MLR +337.99%, MLP -81.56%) conditions. The differences in magnitude between models reflect variation in nonlinear response behavior, particularly under extreme environmental conditions. These results demonstrate the strong influence of

extreme environmental factors on long-term bridge performance and emphasize the importance of incorporating accurate lifetime environmental conditions into infrastructure planning.

3.2. PC vs. CIP Analysis

An adjusted comparative analysis was performed to isolate the effect of deck type using an XGBoost multiclass classification model. CIP bridges were incorporated into the existing dataset of PC bridges, increasing the sample size to over 4,100 bridges while maintaining consistent structural, traffic, and environmental variables. Bridge age was explicitly included to represent deterioration progression and was identified as the dominant predictor, consistent with prior studies (Liu et al., 2018; Morcoux, 2006). The effect of deck type was evaluated across age bins using a counterfactual framework in which all variables were held constant while deck type was alternated between PC and CIP. The marginal effect was quantified as the difference in predicted probability of a bridge being classified in the Good condition state, as defined in Eq. (2). Similar comparisons between PC and CIP systems have been reported in previous studies (Garber and Shahrokhinasab, 2019; Agrawal et al., 2010).

$$\Delta P(G) = P(G|PC) - P(G|CIP) \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta P(G)$ represents the change in predicted probability of being in Good condition when deck type is switched from CIP to PC, holding all other variables constant.

Figure 1. Average difference in predicted probability of a bridge being classified as Good (PC relative to CIP) across age bins.

The predicted probability changes are shown by age group in Figure 1. PC bridges exhibit a positive shift in the probability of being classified as Good in the 20 - 60 year range, while the effect diminishes and becomes negative in later stages. SHAP analysis indicates that bridge age is the dominant predictor (mean $|\text{SHAP}| \approx 0.75$), while deck type contributes a smaller effect (mean $|\text{SHAP}| \approx 0.06$). However, the limited representation of PC bridges in higher age bins introduces uncertainty, and late-life trends should therefore be interpreted cautiously.

4. SUMMARY

This study developed a data-driven framework integrating structural, traffic, and environmental variables to model bridge conditions. Results indicate that environmental factors significantly influence deterioration, with long term environmental conditions shifting condition distributions. Deck type exhibits an age-dependent effect, while bridge age remains the dominant predictor. Future work will extend the framework to covariate-dependent transition modeling using Markov and hybrid ANN-Markov approaches, incorporate environmental uncertainty, and expand across bridge types and regions.

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